

Studies in Benzofurans. Part IV : Synthesis of some 2-Substituted and 2, 3-Disubstituted 3, 4-Dihydro-4-Oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] Pyrimidines

S. B. MAHAJAN* AND Y. S. AGASIMUNDIN**

Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University Post Graduate Centre, Gulbarga-5

Manuscript received 29 November 1976, accepted 25 March 1977

Synthesis of some 3-acylaminobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acids and their transformation into 2-substituted-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidines through 2-substituted-4-H-benzofuro [3, 2-d]-m-oxazin-4-ones and into 2, 3-disubstituted 3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidines by the action of aromatic amines in the presence of phosphorus trichloride is described.

THE importance and the need for the study of benzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidine derivatives has been stressed in our earlier publication¹ and it has been shown that such compounds may conveniently be obtained by constructing pyrimidine ring on suitable benzofuran derivatives. Niementowski reaction has been widely employed for the synthesis of fused pyrimidine systems². Now in an effort to extend this reaction for the synthesis of benzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidines, attempts were made to get the required 3-aminobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid by the hydrolysis of the easily accessible ester (I). Although it could be hydrolysed readily, the acid could not be isolated due to its decarboxylation soon after precipitation. However the hydrolysis of I in alcoholic potash gave the potassium salt of the desired acid in an highly crystalline form. The treatment of this salt with acetic anhydride gave a product which is identified as 2-methyl-4-H-benzofuro [3, 2-d]-m-oxazin-4-one (XIII) on the basis of IR data and elemental analysis. Infrared spectrum shows a strong band at 1780 cm^{-1} characteristic of C=O of such oxazinones³. This is further confirmed by its synthesis through an unambiguous method. Thus I on acetylation and hydrolysis gave 3-acetamidobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid (VII) which on cyclodehydration in acetic anhydride gave an identical product. Treatment of oxazinone (XIII) with ammonia followed by dilute aqueous alkali gave a product which is identified as 2-methyl-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidine (XVII) by comparison with an authentic sample⁴.

Similar cyclodehydration of 3-propionamido, 3-benzamido and 3-phenylacetamidobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acids obtained by the acylation and hydrolysis of I gave the corresponding 2-substituted oxazinones (XIV-XVI) in excellent yields. Infrared spectra of all these compounds exhibit the

characteristic absorption at 1750-1780 cm^{-1} region. 2-Ethyl and 2-benzyl-oxazinones (XIV and XVI) reacted readily with ammonia and aqueous alkali to give 2-ethyl and 2-benzylbenzofuropyrimidinones (XVIII and XIX), but 2-phenyloxazinone failed to undergo a similar reaction under a variety of conditions. Identical products (XVIII and XIX) were obtained by the cyclisation of respective 3-acylamino-benzofuran-2-carboxamides (XI and XII) in presence of dilute aqueous alkali. Both XVIII and XIX exhibit characteristic IR absorptions at 1690 and 3090 cm^{-1} due to C=O and NH respectively of pyrimidinones.

Fused 2, 3-disubstituted 3, 4-dihydro-4-oxopyrimidine systems are best prepared from O-acylamino-carboxylic acids in a single step⁵. Now as a typical example VII is subjected to such a reaction with a few aromatic amines in presence of phosphorus trichloride and the corresponding 2, 3-disubstituted 3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidines (XX-XXVI) were obtained in good yields. The presence of absorption bands at 1680 and 1610-1615 cm^{-1} due to C=O and C=N groups respectively and the absence of any peak in the 3100 cm^{-1} region due to NH group is in agreement with these structures.

All the 3-acylaminobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acids (VII-X) were decarboxylated to the corresponding 3-acylaminobenzofurans (XXVII-XXX) just by heating above their melting points for a few minutes. Further reactions are in progress and will be reported elsewhere.

Experimental

2-Methyl-4-H-benzofuro [3,2-d]-m-oxazin-4-one (XIII) :

To a solution of potassium hydroxide (1.4 g) in

*Department of Chemistry, S. B. College of Science, Gulbarga.

**To whom all the correspondence should be addressed.

- I** R=H; R'=OEt
II R=H; R'=NH₂
III R=COCH₃; R'=OEt
IV R=COCH₂H₅; R'=OEt
V R=COCH₂H₅; R'=OEt
VI R=COCH₂C₆H₅; R'=OEt
VII R=COCH₃; R'=OH
VIII R=COCH₂H₅; R'=OH
IX R=COCH₂C₆H₅; R'=OH
X R=COCH₂C₆H₅; R'=NH₂
XI R=COCH₂H₅; R'=NH₂
XII R=COCH₂C₆H₅; R'=NH₂

- XXVII** R=CH₃
XXVIII R=C₂H₅
XXIX R=C₆H₅
XXX R=CH₂C₆H₅

absolute ethanol (45 ml), ethyl-3-aminobenzofuran-2-carboxylate (1.2g) was added and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about 45 minutes on a water bath. The colourless crystalline potassium salt of 3-amino-benzofuran-2-carboxylic acid starts separating while refluxing. After cooling, the salt was collected by filtration.

The dry salt (1. g) was heated under reflux in acetic anhydride (8 ml) for about 1 hour. The reaction product was poured on ice with stirring. The solid thus separated was collected and crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles (0.75 g), m.p. 151° (Found : C, 65.54 ; H, 3.61 ; N, 6.85, C₁₁H_{7.5}O₃N requires C, 65.67, H, 3.48, N, 6.97%).

Ethyl 3-acetamidobenzofuran-2-carboxylate (III)

I (1 g) was treated with acetic anhydride (4 ml) and then warmed on water bath for 30 minutes. The

- XIII** R=CH₃
XIV R=C₂H₅
XV R=C₆H₅
XVI R=CH₂C₆H₅

- XVII** R=CH₃
XVIII R=C₂H₅
XIX R=CH₂C₆H₅

- XX** R=C₆H₅
XXI R=C₆H₄Cl (p)
XXII R=C₆H₄Br (p)
XXIII R=C₆H₄CH₃ (p)
XXIV R=C₆H₄OCH₃ (p)
XXV R=C₆H₄OC₂H₅ (p)
XXVI R=C₁₀H₇ (p)

reaction product on decomposition with ice water gave a colourless solid.

Similarly ethyl-3-propionamidobenzofuran-2-carboxylate (IV) was prepared by using propionic anhydride. Details are reported in Table 1.

Ethyl-3-benzamidobenzofuran-2-carboxylate (V) :

I (5 g.) was suspended in 2 N aqueous sodium hydroxide (50 ml) and then treated with benzoyl chloride (15 ml) in portions while vigorously shaking. After shaking for 30 minutes the reaction product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from suitable solvent.

Similarly ethyl-3-phenylacetamidobenzofuran-2-carboxylate (VI) was prepared by using phenylacetyl chloride. Details are reported in Table 1.

General method for the preparation of 3-acylamino-benzo furan-2-carboxylic acids (VII-X) :

Ethyl-3-acylamino-benzofuran-2-carboxylate (5 g) was dissolved in suitable volume of ethanol by warming and then treated with a solution of ethanolic potash (2.5 g in 25 ml of ethanol). The reaction mixture was just boiled for 2 minutes, diluted with water and cooled in ice. Acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid liberated the carboxylic acid as colourless solid, which was then filtered, washed with water and crystallised from suitable solvent.

The acids thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE-1

Compound	M.P. °C	S	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Required		Analysis %			
					C	H	N	C	H	N
III	166	a	92	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	63.16	5.26	5.67	63.45	5.51	5.97
IV	142	a	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ N	64.37	5.75	5.36	64.61	5.82	5.57
V	126	a	93	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄ N	69.90	4.85	4.53	70.15	4.53	4.77
VI	157	a	98	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	70.58	5.26	4.33	70.91	5.43	4.71
VII	211(d)	a	85	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N	60.29	4.11	6.39	60.55	4.35	6.68
VIII	205(d)	a	90	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	61.80	4.72	6.01	62.05	4.91	6.33
IX	200(d)	c	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	68.32	3.91	4.98	68.59	4.08	5.21
X	207(d)	b	69	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₄ N	69.15	4.41	4.75	69.35	4.61	4.96
XIII	151	c	72	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ N	65.97	3.48	6.97	65.91	3.52	7.25
XIV	143	c	76	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ N	66.99	4.19	6.51	67.32	4.47	6.73
XV	215	c	76	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₃ N	73.00	3.42	5.32	73.29	3.58	5.61
XVI	151	c	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	73.64	3.97	5.05	73.68	4.11	5.42
XVII	317	d	66	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂	66.01	4.00	14.01	66.17	4.15	14.34
XVIII	319	d	65	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	67.30	4.67	13.08	67.55	4.72	13.29
XIX	283	d	60	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂	73.91	4.35	10.15	74.07	4.44	10.21
XX	235	b	58	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	73.91	4.35	10.15	74.12	4.39	10.27
XXI	209	b	97	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	65.69	3.54	9.02	65.91	3.66	9.43
XXII	208	c	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	57.46	3.10	7.89	57.64	3.31	8.02
XXIII	253	b	69	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	74.49	4.83	9.66	74.57	5.01	9.87
XXIV	194	b	63	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	70.60	4.58	9.15	70.81	4.73	9.37
XXV	209	c	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	71.25	5.00	8.76	71.40	5.12	8.91
XXVI	197	c	50	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	77.31	4.29	8.59	77.50	4.41	8.77
XXVII	169	a	80	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ N	68.58	5.14	8.00	68.73	5.20	8.35
XXVIII	156	a	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	69.84	5.82	7.41	70.11	5.97	7.91
XXIX	130	c	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	75.97	4.64	5.91	76.19	4.81	6.30
XXX	140	a	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	76.49	5.18	5.58	76.55	5.29	5.61

S = Solvent of crystallisation ; a = aqueous ethanol ; b = ethanol ; c = benzene-petroleum ether ; d = aqueous DMF.

General method for the preparation of 2-substituted 4-H-benzofuro [3, 2-d]-m-oxazin-4-ones (XIII-XVI) :

3-Acylaminobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid (2 g) was heated under reflux in acetic anhydride (8 ml) for about 1 hour. Excess of acetic anhydride was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residual product was treated with petroleum ether and the crystalline solid thus obtained was collected and crystallised from suitable solvent. Mixed m.p. of 2-methyl-4-H-benzofuro-[3, 2-d]-m-oxazin-4-one with the sample obtained by the earlier method was not depressed.

Melting point, yield, analytical data etc. of the compounds thus prepared are summarised in Table 1.

General method for the preparation of 2-substituted 3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidines (XVII-XIX) :

Benzofuro-oxazinone (1 g) was suspended in liquor ammonia (10 ml) and refluxed on water bath for about 1 hour. A solution of 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (5 ml) was then added and refluxed for further 10 minutes. The reaction product was filtered and the clear filtrate when acidified with acetic acid gave the corresponding 2-substituted 3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidine as colourless solid. Solvent of crystallisation, m.p. yield, analytical results etc. of the compounds thus prepared are summarised in Table 1.

3-Propionamidobenzofuran-2-carboxamide (XI) :

II (2 g) was treated with propionic anhydride

(8 ml) and warmed till a clear solution was obtained. The reaction product on decomposition with ice gave XI, which on crystallisation from aqueous ethanol was obtained as colourless needles, (2.2 g), m.p. 169° (Found : C, 62.38 ; H, 5.44 ; N, 12.38, C₁₂H₁₂O₂N₂ requires C, 62.07 ; H, 5.17 ; N, 12.07%).

3-Phenylacetamidobenzofuran-2-carboxamide (XII) :

II (2 g) was suspended in 2N aqueous sodium hydroxide (20 ml) and treated with phenylacetyl chloride (4 ml). The reaction mixture was shaken vigorously, for 30 minutes, cooled and filtered. On crystallisation from aqueous ethanol it was obtained as colourless needles, (2.6 g.), m.p. 189° (Found : C, 69.61 ; H, 4.83 ; N, 9.78, C₁₇H₁₄O₂N₂ requires C, 69.39 ; H, 4.76 ; N, 9.53%).

2-Ethyl-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidine (XVIII) :

XI (12 g) was suspended in 2 N aqueous sodium hydroxide (600 ml) and warmed till a clear solution was obtained. The alkaline solution on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid gave XVIII, as a solid, which on crystallisation from aqueous DMF was obtained as colourless needles, (9 g) m.p. 319°. Mixed m.p. with the sample obtained above was not depressed (Found : C, 67.55 ; H, 4.83 ; N, 13.41, C₁₂H₁₂O₂N₂ requires C, 67.30 ; H, 4.67 ; N, 13.08%).

2-Benzyl-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidine (XIX) :

XII (12 g) was treated with 2N aqueous sodium hydroxide (600 ml) until a clear solution was obtained subsequent working up as above gave, XIX as colourless solid (6.5 g). It was crystallised from aqueous DMF as colourless needles, m.p. 283°. Mixed m.p. with the sample obtained by the above method was not depressed (Found ; C, 74.15 ; H, 4.51 ; N, 10.38, $C_{17}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73.91 ; H, 4.35 ; N, 10.15%).

General Procedure for the synthesis of 2-methyl-3-aryl-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro [3, 2-d] pyrimidines (XX-XXXI) :

3-Acetamidobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid (VII, 0.01 mole) and aromatic amine (0.01 mole) were dissolved in dry toluene (25 ml) and a solution of phosphorus trichloride (0.6 ml) in dry toluene (5 ml) was added in portions with vigorous shaking. After the addition is over the reaction mixture was heated under reflux in an oil bath at 130° for 2 to 4 hours. The reaction product, after cooling was treated with 10% aqueous sodium carbonate (25 ml) and then subjected to steam distillation to remove toluene. The crystalline solid thus separated was collected and crystallised from suitable solvent. Crystallisation solvent, m.p. yield, analytical data etc. are recorded in Table 1.

3-Acylaminobenzofurans (XXVII-XXX) :

3-Acylaminobenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid (1 g) was heated above its melting point for about 40 minutes. The product was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and the insoluble material so obtained was crystallised from suitable solvent. Compounds thus prepared are described in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their grateful thanks to Prof. E. S. Jayadevappa and Dr. S.P. Hiremath for their interest and encouragement, to Dr. R.S. Hosmane, University of South Florida, Tampa, U.S.A. for I.R. spectra and to Shri V.A. Desai and Dr.G.S. Gadaginamath for the microanalysis.

References :

1. (Miss) S. S. Sangapure and Y. S. Agasimundin, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976 (in press).
2. V. S. Patel and S. R. Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 531 ; 1967, 45, 197 and 1970, 47, 125.
3. S. W. Schneller and F. W. Clough, *J. heterocycl. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 513.
4. (Miss) S. S. Sangapure and Y. S. Agasimundin, Unpublished work.
5. H. W. Grimmel, A. Guenther and J. F. Morgan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 542.